

Authors' Response to Reviews of

An appraisal of Daylight Saving Time, a solution for which many forgot the problems

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Royal Society Open Science 12 (3) 240727. doi, 10.1098/rsos.240727

RC: *Reviewers' Comment*, AR: Authors' Response, □ Manuscript Text

Round 1. Dated 14 September 2024 09:30CEST

Authors' responses DOI: 10.1098/RSOS.240727/V2/RESPONSE1

We want to thank the Reviewers and the Editorial Office for their comments and for the opportunity to submit a revised version.

We agree with the Reviewers' comments that "science only progresses through open debate" and that "it is important to challenge potential group-think and really critically evaluate this issue and some assumptions that may have become embedded in the discourse." Our effort in bringing this manuscript was clearly prompted by these points.

We take this revised version as an opportunity to sharpen our arguments after the wonderful exchange with reviewers that RSOS has provided.

1. Summary of the changes in the revised version

There are major changes in the revision version following or inspired by reviewers' comments to the initial submission.

Here, we would like to summarize the changes and provide an overall description.

We first put forward that the title of the manuscript was amended. In the initial submission it read "An appraisal of Daylight Saving Time, a solution for which many forgot the problems".

The new title runs: "Assessing the best hour to start the day: an appraisal of seasonal Daylight Saving Time" which keeps the central idea of the initial submission and puts forward the fundamental question addressed by the clock regulations: the best hour to start the day. We hope it is catchy and understandable for any potential reader.

More formally, the "best hour to start the day" refers to the timing of human activity or the phase of human activity. We make every effort in the new submission to link clock regulations with the timing (phase) of human activity. Our manuscript does not deal with "phase angle of entrainment". We do not analyse differences in the phase of human activity and the phase of some biological cycles (for instance cortisol). We focus on environmental conditions (morning light) and social/human preferences.

The layout/sectioning of the manuscript was slightly altered.	28
Two more figures have been added, for a total of three.	29
References have grown from 83 to 112.	30
We have submitted as Supplementary Material four more figures.	31
Word count has also dramatically increase.	32
We now summarize changes by section. Very briefly: section 2 (rationale), section 5 (chronic effect/misalignment) and section 8 (conclusions) have been very much altered. The remaining sections have been slightly altered.	33 34
1.1. Section 1: Introduction	35
The first two paragraphs of the Introduction kick off the goals of the manuscript in a slightly different way following suggestions from Reviewer 1, 2 and 4. We have also put forward in the 1st paragraph a sketch of the political issues related to DST. In the 2nd paragraph we now address the question that this manuscript addresses. Indeed, it is the question addressed by DST regulations.	36 37 38 39
The second paragraph prints out that clock regulations relate to the timing of human cycle. We have made every effort to make this clear.	40 41
Aside from that, Section 1 contains only slight amends.	42
1.2. Section 2: rationale behind clock regulations	43
Section 2 mostly tells the same arguments posted in the initial version, but it has been largely rephrased, hopefully for the best.	44 45
Title section changed to “what are clock regulations meant for” .	46
We only describe in this section the rationale behind clock regulations. We moved the association of clock regulations to time zones to Section 5.	47 48
The first two paragraphs address the research question in full detail. They also address one issue posted by reviewer 4 in their comments. We make every effort to make it clear that our question refers to the timing or phase of the human cycles. We never make use of the concept of “phase entrainment” or the like, which is different and more specialized.	49 50 51 52
Then, it follows the comparison between Bogotá and New York, largely rephrased. We have introduced equations 1 and 2, where SRW (winter sunrise time) and SRS (sunrise time in summer) are presented as a function of latitude and of the axial tilt.	53 54 55
We then present previous studies that reports the delay of the human cycles with latitude. We have now added one more study by Sani et al. [1]. Following a comment by reviewer 2 we provide a description of the studies.	56 57
Figures have slightly changed, hopefully for the best. In the initial submission Figure 1 consisted of three panels. In the revised version Figure 1 shows only two panels: panels (a) and (c) in the initial submission. That way Figure 1 describes seasonal variations connected to sunrise (morning).	58 59 60
We have also included here a series of studies that show seasonal variations in rise times and in bedtimes, that go in line with clock regulations. In the initial submission, some of these studies were described in Section 4	61 62

(Misalignment).	63
Figure 2 consists of two panel, one of which (panel a) is brand-new, and the remaining panel is Figure 1b of the initial submission.	64 65
Figure 2a describes seasonal variations at the central hour of the day. Finally, Figure 2b allows a visualization of the seasonal variation in the afternoon and evening, as well as a global view in a full day.	66 67
As in the initial submission, Section 2 ends with a description of the limitations of our simplified model. We now include a brand-new figure, figure 3, where human daily rhythms in Italy and Finland are shown and put in context with SRW, SRS, SSS and clock regulations.	68 69 70
1.3. Section 3: short-term impact of transition dates	71
Only minor changes following reviewers' comments.	72
1.4. Section 4: setting transition dates	73
Former section 5 is now promoted to section 4	74
At the beginning of the section a new paragraph introduces the issue of transition dates.	75
Section title changed to "setting transition dates".	76
1.5. Section 5: chronic impact/misalignment	77
This section has been largely rephrased and enlarged. Also it was moved after section 4 (setting transition dates).	78 79
With this new layout we first address (section 3 and 4) the "classical" issues associated with clock regulations: short-term effect and setting transition dates. Then, section 5 addresses the modern criticism to clock regulations, associated with chronic, long-term effects, misalignment, and "wrong time zones".	80 81 82
We begin the section recalling the association between clock regulations and time zones that was placed on section 2 in the initial submission.	83 84
In the initial submission we discussed here previous studies that show seasonal variations in the timing of human cycles. In this new version these paragraphs were moved to section 2.	85 86
We have rephrased the paragraph related to sleep loss throughout DST following a comment by reviewer 2.	87
Following a comment by reviewer 4 we address social jet lag (SjL).	88
Following a comment by reviewer 2 we have added one paragraph that report known adaptive response to clock regulations (paragraph third to last) and we have rephrased the lack of response to seasonal clock regulations (paragraph second to last).	89 90 91
1.6. Sections 6 and 7	92
These sections have been slightly amended following reviewers' comments.	93

1.7. Section 8: Concluding remarks	94
The concluding section has been totally rephrased following criticism by reviewers.	95
As we put forward in this section, we do not have a bold concluding remark: clock regulations must come to an end, or clock regulations must continue. We just describe the rationale behind which clock regulations have succeeded. If anything, we may put forward a well-known saying: “if it ain’t broke, don’t fix it”.	96 97 98
2. Detailed response to Reviewer 1	99
Reviewer’s comments DOI: 10.1098/RSOS.240727/V1/REVIEW1 Reviewer 1 is anonymous.	100 101
We thank reviewer 1 for their constructive report and comments.	102
RC: 1) I would like to note a fairly recent review that would fit well to the introduction, namely: Saving human lives: D. Helbing et al., What complexity science and information systems can contribute, J. Stat. Phys. 158, 735-781 (2015), where similar issues have been covered with an emphasis on computational and data driven approaches.	103 104 105 106
AR: We thank very much the reviewer for this comment. We start our manuscript highlighting the importance of synchronizing mechanisms in modern societies. We also stress that clock regulations are one of these synchronizing mechanisms. It is, indeed, one characteristic of clock regulations that is usually forgotten. We added a citation to Pal et al. [2].	107 108 109 110
RC: 2) It might also improve the paper if the figure captions would also consider a sentence or two saying what is the main message of the presented results in each figure.	111 112
AR: Thank you very much. This is highly convenient. Our first sentence in the figure caption intends to do so.	113
3. Detailed response to Reviewer 2	114
Reviewer’s comments DOI: 10.1098/RSOS.240727/V1/REVIEW2 Reviewer 2 is Michael C. Antle.	115 116
We thank reviewer 2 for their thorough read of our manuscript, for signaling many omissions and for addressing some critical issues that hopefully would help to improve the revised version.	117 118
RC: 1. The figure presented is highly problematic. a. For panel a, the right-hand y-axis label is confusing. Perhaps: “Sunrise time difference between the equinox and solstice”	119 120
AR: We thank reviewer 2 for this comment. Indeed, their choice is most adequate.	121
RC: b. panel a is hard to read, the equinox line is almost invisible, and the dark water and white land are the inverse of what is expected.	122 123
AR: We have amended the picture in line with this comment. Hopefully for the best.	124
RC: c. panel b (and throughout the manuscript): the terms P1-P4 are very hard to follow, as they are arbitrary labels that provide no information as to what they indicate. P1 is sunrise in winter, P2 is sunrise in	125 126

summer, p3 is sunset in summer and p4 is sunset in winter. Instead, the authors might abbreviate these to something meaningful, like SunSetWinter (SSW) or SunRiseSummer (SRS). This would aid the reader in understanding the point without having to continually refer back to the figure.

AR: We agree that the choices SSW, SRS and the like are more descriptive. We stick to that in this new version. Thank you for this suggestion.

RC: *d. Similarly, the term Q1 is not well described. It seems to refer to a point 1h ahead of the sunrise on the winter equinox, to simulate sunrise with DST. This is confusing for a number of reasons. First, very few places currently have DST on the winter equinox, including NYC, the reference location for the Q1 point. This is a strange argument to make as it does not represent a situation that exists, nor one that the author is proposing. The description of this on lines 17-44 on page 3 really needs to be rewritten to clearly explain why Q1 is set where it is and what this means. Perhaps vertical lines to represent the average wake-up time on ST and DST would get the point across to the novice reader, as this expert reader struggled.*

AR: The reviewer should note that we seldom refer to clock time in our manuscript. We mostly refer to mean solar time. Q1 (SRW⁻ in the new version) is one hour ahead for the winter sunrise time (SRW). SRW is determined by latitude, so is SRW⁻. Also, the reviewer should note that SRW⁻ is irrespective of whether clock regulations apply.

The lines 1-44 on page 3 in the original submission described the impact of latitude on sunrise times and the rationale behind the clock regulations.

In this revised version we show the daily rhythms of wake and of work in Finland and Italy (figure 3). Solar ephemerides are annotated in this figure.

RC: *e. I think something is missing in panel c. I think that this presents the sun's height in the sky at 6:26am (the time of sunrise on the winter equinox). As DST moves down later by an hour, at 6:26am on DST, the sun is lower on the horizon at this time than on StdT. The P2 line is confusing too, as this represents the sun's height at 4:34 (sunrise time on the summer solstice throughout the year, or part of it). The sun height from October to mid-March is not presented but would be visible on the chart in October when StdT resumes.*

AR: For clarification the thick-dashed-thick line shows the sun height at P1 (SRW) and the dashed-thick-dashed line shows the sun height one hour earlier (Q1, SRW⁻).

The thin line in the initial submission was the sun height at SRS, which is always negative: the sun is below the horizon at this hour of the day. This line has now been removed.

This figure includes now two new lines corresponding to 06:00 mean solar time. It helps to visualize differences with the Equator, where the sun is at the horizon at 06:00 always. The second one corresponds to SRW⁼ (two hours ahead of SRW). It helps to visualize the rationale behind a seasonal double daylight saving time. Later we describe why seasonal dDST is not a choice.

RC: *f. The yellow zigzag lines are not really explained in the document very well in this manuscript (just 3 lines on page 5 (lines 44-46)), and reference a proposal put forward by the main author in a different paper.*

AR: We have added context in the revised version. We hesitated about the zigzag lines but in the end our choice is to keep them visible, due to the new context added.

As an example, individuals can set their alarm clocks 15 min earlier three weeks before the spring

transition date. Set the clock 15 min minutes earlier two weeks, and one week before the transition; and reset the alarm clock to their regular value after the transition. The individual would complete a 4-stroke, 15 min transition, smoother than the clock regulations (see zigzag lines in Figure 1b). Chances that scores of population would behave like that are negligible small, because people abhor a change in their regular rhythms. Nonetheless, for those worried by the impact of the one-hour stroke it is a sensible choice that could be easily preset in cellular as an option.

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RC: 2. *The first sentence on page 2, “one of the most significant issues in which science, society and policy interplay” seems like an overstatement. This debate likely pales in comparison to climate change, an issue where “science, society, and policy interplay”.*

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AR: We have amended this sentence. Now it reads “one of the most visible issues”, in line with reviewer 4 comment.

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RC: 3. *Page 2 line 10, “Seasonal changing of start times”. This is a central concept of the authors’ thesis argument and is not described in a convincing or clear fashion. Does this refer to everyone essentially waking an hour earlier on DST, or is this referring to the human circadian clock tracking dawn as it changes over the year? If the latter, this needs to be clearly explained with evidence.*

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AR: We have made every effort to clarify this point in the revised version.

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We refer to everyone essentially waking an hour earlier in spring-summer compared to autumn-winter. Currently this is achieved by clock regulations. Earlier, seasonal preset schedules were also a choice. We now report studies under more naturalistic conditions that report earlier rise times in summer.

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RC: 4. *Page 2 line 41 “... ignore the issues that DST addressed and helped to solve (related to “early” summer sunrise).” What is the evidence that early sunrise is a problem? Figure 1 in Kantermann 2007 demonstrates that the human circadian clock is able to compensate for early sunrises in the summer when the photoperiod is quite long. Avoiding early sunrises is frequently raised as a concern by DST proponents, but the evidence that these early sunrises cause a problem has not been demonstrated.*

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AR: Our wording was not accurate. In the revised version we have rephrased this paragraph in order to make clear that the issues relate to the delay of start times/onset times relative to the (early) sunrise.

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The clearest evidence of the problems associated with “late” onset times in Extratropical societies bound to preset time schedules is the very existence of clock regulations and their long sustainability.

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We do not mean that a late start of human activity, is an issue from a healthy point of view. It is rather that (some) people/societies find outcomes in advancing the phase of their activity in spring-summer, when the sun rises earlier. In other words, they find relief in not delaying the start of their activity too much relative to sunrise time.

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Again, we do not mean that because of that people/societies must practice clock regulations. Only that some find relief in doing that.

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RC: 5. *Lines 11-13 on page 3 claims that seasonal DST is “imperfectly mimicking ancient seasonal regulation of the human activity”. The evidence behind the claim of “seasonal regulation of the human activity” needs to be presented and described. Also, the claim that earlier “office hours” are available in the spring/summer seems to rest only on the fact that it is daylight earlier, ignoring the ability of the human circadian clock to adjust phase angle of entrainment to maintain a steady wake time despite an expanding photoperiod throughout the spring (Kantermann et al. 2007).*

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AR: We took the ancient seasonal regulation of the human activity as self-evident in the initial submission. We have rephrased the paragraph. We cite a study on the mechanisms of seasonal cycles of behaviour in life. The new wording goes as:

The hypothesis of a “misalignment” throughout DST is elusive if only because pre-modern human activity should have displayed, under a more naturalistic environment, the seasonal behaviour that characterize many living forms in Extratropical latitudes.[3, 4] In section 2 we presented a series of studies showing a seasonal change in the timing of human cycles.[5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10]

On the second part of the comment, yes. Our claim rests in the fact that the sun rises earlier. The whole rationale behind clock regulations is the fact at above some latitude the spread of sunrise times is large enough.

After the winter solstice and with the sun rising earlier and earlier, more and more people find outcomes in starting their day earlier. The preferences must be impacted by the chronotype of the individual and also by the economic sector.

We do not claim that wake-up times must track the sunrise perfectly. Therefore, our claim is not challenged by the observations in Kantermann et al. [11]. A perfect match between wake-up and sunrise in spring-summer is not possible beyond a circle of latitude (think of the Polar Circles as an extreme scenario). It is not possible now; it was not possible in ancient times, either. We addressed this issue later in page 3 lines 35-40 (initial submission). We (following Hudson) just claim that SRW may not hold as a choice for wake-up times throughout the calendar year above a circle of latitude. Many people can find SRW a valid, sensible choice for the start of the day in winter; but many will not find SRW a valid choice in summer.

RC: 6. *The paragraph on page 3, lines 17-22 needs expanding. A number of studies are listed with no details. Given the arguments, the reader would benefit from describing in what ways the delay in sunrise in winter impacts social metrics.*

AR: Details are provided in the revised version. We also added the study Sani et al. [1]. Inspired by this comment we have described many of the studies that are cited in the revised version.

RC: 7. *line 24, page 3 “Around the spring Equinox the sun rises at 06:00 irrespective of latitude.” This is only true for cities that lie along the longitude that defines their time zone. This is also not true in North America in the spring where the equinox falls after the start of DST, and is also not true in most of the northern hemisphere in the autumn, since the switch to StdT occurs long after the autumn equinox.*

AR: Irrespective of latitude the photoperiod is 12 h around the Equinoxes. Therefore, sunrise and sunset occur at 06:00 and 18:00. We meant mean solar time. We seldom refer to clock time. Clock time is a sub-optimal quantity to deal with in a scientific context. Specifically in the context of clock regulations, the use of clock time is surrounded by confusion.

RC: 8. *Page 3, line 34 “only in the same sense as ‘office hours’ are artificial”. Office hours likely emerged from patterns of human social behavior prior to mechanical clocks, in line with the authors’ rule of thumb “duty first before pleasure” (p7, line45). Schools and non-shift-work jobs follow this pre-clock tradition, suggesting that “office hours” may represent human biology rather than simply an artificial social construct. Certainly, this pattern of behavior is apparent in pre-industrialized societies where there are no “office hours” (Smit et al, 2019)*

AR: Thank you very much for this comment. We mostly agree. Here we intended to link “office hour” (or preset time schedules, or social clock if you like) to the social artificial construct. As an example, the necessity that

a commuter must leave at a given hour of the day, and that hour of the day must be known in advance by the individuals. Or schools, universities must start the duties at a given, predictable hour of the day. It is in this sense that they are “artificial”, and indeed synchronizing.

On the other side, of course “office hours” are linked to human physiology. Societies never choose to start their activity at midnight, as an example. Schools and universities rather prefer to start their duties in the photoperiod. Start times (work onset and sleep offset) associate then with the SRW[12, 13, 14].

In this line our main goal is to unveil the link between human physiology and clock regulations. Clock regulations are not randomly (artificially) designed. They follow a pattern that can be linked with natural conditions: align start times closer to sunrise. We hope that in this new version this point of view is better described.

A citation to Smit et al. [15] was added in another context. The study shows, under naturalistic, Tropical conditions, that sleep offset entrains to sunrise, while sleep onset does not entrain to sunset.

RC: *9. Lines 37-39 on page 3 are not clear. Are the authors saying that we don't further advance the clocks to use the even earlier dawns of late spring/ early summer because the adjusted sunset would affect sleep. Again, like point 5 above, this ignores the ability of the circadian clock to adjust phase angle of entrainment with expanding photoperiods. Also, as written this is difficult to understand. DST moves sunset further away from the end of “office hours”, so the authors must be intending to say that this would move sunset so later that it is closer to the start of "office hours" the following day.*

AR: We agree with reviewer 2 that the paragraph was poorly written. Nonetheless reviewer 2 got the point. Yes, an interval of morning photoperiod may not be harvested during the summer season. The reason for that is the shortening of the scotoperiod with increasing latitude.

In the revised version we post the following paragraph:

Seasonal changes at dusk are symmetrical to those described at dawn. Figure 2b shows two clocks with 24 h analog dials with the permanent night (dark red), the permanent day (light yellow) and the hours of the day with day or night condition depending on season. SRW , SRW^- and $SRW^=$ are annotated in either clock, which is set at 40° latitude (left) and at 52° latitude (right), the latitude of London and Berlin. We note that SRW and SSS (summer sunset time) are always differ in 12 h. Therefore SRW^- and SSS always differ in 11 h. Harvesting earlier morning hours in midsummer, like $SRW^=$ (see Figure 1b), comes with a challenging issue: SSS differ 10 h from $SRW^=$, a shorter interval that can jeopardize bedtimes. In the end a seasonal double DST has seldom been employed and only in connection with war times or crises (Portugal 1942-1945, and Germany 1945 and 1947).

From another perspective a second stroke of one hour around late spring-early summer (a double DST) would bring sunset clock times too late in summer, and increasing shares of population would show discomfort with this setting. We also refer to comment 5 (lines 11-13 on page 3) by reviewer 2.

A rule of thumb is that start times earlier than 06:00 mean solar time (Equatorial sunrise time and yearly averaged sunrise time) are increasingly difficult to achieve.

RC: *10. lines 47-49 on page 3 “Early risers, those with starting points earlier than P1, are less needed of a further advance of the clocks in spring. Late risers, those with starting points later than P1, need more a further advance of the clocks in spring.” This is not clear, I think something was lost in translation.*

AR: Thank you very much for noting this. We agree and we have rephrased this.

Early risers, those with onset times earlier than SRW, find little benefits in advancing the clocks in spring because they already have an advanced phase of activity. Late risers, those with onset times aligned to SRW find more benefits in aligning the work hours closer to sunrise in spring.

RC: *11. Last line of page 4. The authors cite the European Commission “the issue that caused inconvenience was the changing of the clocks”. Much of the arguments that follow focus on the loss of an hour of sleep and “reentrainment” to the new time. The problem with these arguments is that the evidence is that the human circadian clock does not re-entrain to the new time (Kantermann 2007), but rather continues to track the photoperiod. It is this chronic misalignment between the social schedule and the circadian clock that makes the DST time change so much harder to deal with a regular night of poor sleep.*

AR: The cited sentence is extracted from the summary of a public hearing held at the European Parliament in March 2015 where clock regulations were discussed. The document quotes “experts presentations covering the aspects of road safety, health, better law-making and energy”. Later we can read that at least one of the health experts was a chronobiologist. Therefore, we understand that in this summary sentence the European Parliament is taking into consideration the health issues shown at that public hearing, that may have well included Kantermann et al. [11].

We take this opportunity to highlight that the referred study is limited to one country/region: Central Europe, meaning essentially Germany. Things can be different elsewhere because (1) latitude plays a role; (2) the phase of human activity changes. Germany has a more advanced phase of human activity compared to United Kingdom.[13, 16] When making this comparison we meant mean solar time, not clock time.

We have problems to address the “circadian misalignment” properly and the “chronic circadian misalignment” beyond the point that they look “bad things” to have, and they are related to the DST period.

Reviewer 2 suggests that the human circadian clock does not “re-entrain” to the new time but rather “tracks the photoperiod”. In our perspective this looks totally fine. As mentioned earlier we do not think that Kantermann et al. [11] challenge our position.

RC: *12. lines 44-46 page 5. The authors suggest, based on their prior work, that circadian preadaptation could solve the problems caused by the abrupt 1h time changes we already use. This suggestion ignores the problem of entrainment mentioned earlier, instead extending the circadian misalignment over an extra 3 weeks. Furthermore, while there is no agreement among the public on if we should move to permanent StdT or permanent DST, the public is united in their desire to not change the clocks twice a year. Suggesting the solution is to now change them 8 times a year is unlikely to garner support from the public*

AR: Reviewer 2 missed one important phrase in our argument. We said, “on an individual basis”. We are not demanding 8 changes of the clock per year. Among many other factors, the safety in public transportation and the coordination with foreign partners would not allow that. We hope our new wording (see author response to reviewer 2 comment 1f) clarifies our point.

RC: *13. Lines 4-6 page 6 The authors ponder: “Why are New York residents misaligned when they start their activity on Q1 after the spring transition, while Bogota residents are not?”. The New Yorkers are misaligned because they are required to wake an hour earlier than their circadian clocks would prefer, while Bogota residents do not change their clocks and have a stable sunrise time year-round.*

AR: We think this is a most important comment and in the revised version we have made every effort to clarify our point.

In short, we do not think that “they [New Yorkers] are required to wake an hour earlier than their circadian

clocks would prefer” is a thorough answer to this question. The stability of the phase (timing) of the sleep/wake cycle is one important thing to consider, but it is not the only factor that enters in the discussion. 307 308

The critical thing here is that New Yorkers *are not required* to do that. Rather, they are *invited* to do so. They could have been fooled one year: 1918, when they started changing the clocks. Perhaps they could have been fooled for two years, or for three years, maybe for ten. But the lack of adaptive response to clock regulations in the past 106 years, specifically the sustainability of clock regulations and the lack of delayed wake-up times during the summer season is evidence that they *are not required to do that* but, instead, *they willingly do that*. They do not feel *misaligned*, or they are only slightly *misaligned*. 309 310 311 312 313 314

Alternatively, we may consider that the delay of sunrise in winter is a powerful stressor that is able to delay the timing of human cycles in autumn-winter with latitude. However, “keeping the phase” is not strong enough after the first stressor vanished around the spring Equinox. 315 316 317

Also, at the Concluding remarks we now add the following idea: 318

We maintain that much of the current discussion is focused on the phase (timing) of human activity in summer because its extended daytime allows different layouts for human activity without challenging key aspects of human physiology. While medical associations would love delayed times in summer, many still love the current setting and enjoy their longer leisure time in daylight. We do not exclude that a delay of the phase in summer might yield benefits in some key health issues, yet we sustain that the lack of adaptive responses and the fact that morning, pre-modern, ancient activity was probably like the current setting, suggest that these benefits might be marginal. Seasonal clock regulations do not play against human physiology.

Aside from that, the question to commented by reviewer 2 has been moved to another location in the corresponding section. We also describe thanks to figure 1b and figure 2a that spring-summer morning in Bogotá and New York are more alike than in autumn-winter, which intuitively should lead to more alike human activity. 319 320 321 322

RC: *14. The arguments in the 3rd paragraph on page 6 do not follow logically and are not supported with evidence. First, the loss of 20 minutes of sleep is dismissed as being trivial as it amounts to only 5 % of sleep. Where is the evidence that loss of this much is inconsequential? Next, this is compared to night over the year “night time changes by 100 % in Germany from summer to winter”. I think the authors are saying that the length of the night doubles from 8h in the summer to 16h in the winter, a 100* 323 324 325 326 327

AR: Thank you very much for this comment. We have reworded the issues related to sleep loss and added more context. We still quote that this reported sleep loss is ~ 5 % of the daily sleep. Not meaning it is trivial. It is just what it is. 328 329 330

RC: *15. Page 6, line 42, The authors conclude “they would have taken action by delaying their preset time schedules in summer to offset the ’misalignment’”. Why is this reasonable that this would have happened? There are many factors at play, and the debate over DST for the last 30 years has demonstrated that even with strong public debate, changes are slow to happen even when there is a will. Just because action hasn’t been taken does not mean that no one wants to take action.* 331 332 333 334 335

AR: We have added a paragraph (third to last in the section) to clarify our point: 336

Adaptive responses to clock regulations are indeed known in history. When Spain (mainland) remained 337

in the Central European Time (UTC+1) after World War Two, one hour ahead of the sun clock, social preset schedules continued to entrain to the sun clock, meaning that they apparently “delayed” by clock time. This response is still surrounded by confusion to many.[17, 18] When permanent DST was tested in United Kingdom and in Ireland (1970), in United States (1973), in Portugal (1967), in Russia (2011) or in Chile (2015) the setting did not sustain: the discomfort brought by start times ahead of the sunrise in winter, lead to its cancelling. When Portugal (1992) advanced their clocks by one hour year-round to align them with Central European Time; the setting survived only three years and, seemingly, caused a political crisis.

No such adaptive responses are known regarding the application of summertime during the spring, summer seasons in Europe and America. On the contrary, the inception of clock regulations can be understood as a responsive action against the discomfort that start times aligned to SRW brought in the spring, summer seasons.

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Some authors draw conclusions from previous failures to sustain permanent DST in United Kingdom, in United States and elsewhere, which is perfectly fine.[18, 19] But choose to ignore the fact that seasonal clock regulations did sustain in these countries for more than one hundred years.[20]

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We make clear our point here: by design (spring forward; instead of backward) and goals, the primary consequence of clock regulations is the advance of rise times after the spring transition. A primary response to this external stressor would be a delay of wake times during the spring-summer season. This is seldom observed.

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RC: *16. page 6 line 53 A citation is needed to support the claim that “This result is in line with the current behaviour in societies under clock regulations, which also find earlier rise times and earlier bedtimes during in summer.”*

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Thank you very much for this comment. We will add some references.

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The key phrase here is “under clock regulations”. Year-round rise times under clock regulations mean earlier rise times in summer, late in winter.

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RC: *17. Last line of page 6 “incorporation of human activity into the dark hours of the winter morning, now possible with the use of artificial light”. Artificial light might allow people to see, but it is likely insufficient to entrain the human circadian clock which requires much brighter light (Czeisler 1989) than is found in most workplaces.*

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AR: We could not agree any more. We just note that some people are finding outcomes in harvesting the dark hours of the winter morning thanks to artificial light.

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RC: *18. page 7 line 12 “growing extension” needs to be reworded.*

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Thank you very much for this comment. We have amended the paragraph according to this remark.

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RC: *19. page 7 line 16, the authors present a really good argument here on when the DST transitions should occur.*

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AR: Thank you very much.

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RC: *20. page 7 line 18 the following phrase is unclear and should be reworded “...must be done before scores of population start facing...”*

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AR: Thank you very much again. We amended this sentence.

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RC: 21. page 7 line 21 the more common plural form of equinox is equinoxes; equinoctes is a rare and archaic form. 366
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AR: Thank you very much. Noted. 368

RC: 22. page 7 lines 26-27 “dark hours of the morning, which leads to a higher number of accidents”. While darkness likely contributes somewhat, the problem here is not so much the darkness, but the fact that the drives are operating their vehicles an hour earlier than their circadian clocks are ready to, so the drivers are sleepy, a well-known risk factor when operating a motor vehicle. 369
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AR: We are not excluding factors. Both are contributing factors. One is associated with accidents occurring around the sunrise. The second one propagates during the whole day, and it is bigger in size. Fritz et al. [21], noted by Martín-Olalla [22], show that the morning IRR doubled after the Energy Policy Act brought spring transition three weeks earlier and a larger share of population needed to commute in the dark hours of the morning. 373
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RC: 23. The last two sentences of page 7 are not clear (lodestar??), and again seems to ignore circadian entrainment compensating in long photoperiods. Just because the sun is up does not mean a person is ready to be awake. 377
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AR: We are not saying that the sunrise must dictate human daily rhythm in the sense that, for instance, an individual should wake always exactly by the sunrise, again think of the Polar Circle as an extreme scenario. Hopefully we have already made this point clear. We do mean that human activity friendly resumes in ambient light, around, close, in the vicinity of sunrise. 380
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Also “lodestar”: “one [star] that serves as an inspiration, model, or guide” (Webster Dictionary); “a ‘guiding star’; that on which one’s attention or hopes are fixed” (Oxford English Dictionary). 384
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In the new version we replaced “lodestar” by “cue”. 386

RC: 24. page 8 line 17-18. Citation needed. 387

AR: We had presented arguments that human activity is prone to seasons in Section 2 and section 4. Generally speaking, most living animals shows seasonal variations under naturalistic conditions. We have rephrased the paragraph and included a citation. 388
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RC: 25. page 8 line 20. This sentence needs revising, I think something was lost in translation “While it looks fancy to anyone having the clocks locked, the problems arise in the following minute because the circadian clock, the mechanical clock, the preset schedules, and the cycle of light and dark cannot conciliate at midlatitudes.” 391
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AR: Thank you very much for this comment. We have amended the sentence: 395

While locking the clocks may look fine to anyone, the problems arise in the following minute because the circadian clock, the mechanical clock, and the preset schedules —the three of them prone to a fixed 24 h period— cannot conciliate well with the timing of light and dark at midlatitudes, which does not observe this period.

RC: 26. page 8 lines 29-31. These are not equivalent choices. The former allows the individual to adjust their schedule out of personal preference, while the latter imposes an earlier awakening on society. The argument around line 33 similarly ignores the integration of various sectors of society, such as schools that essentially provide childcare for families while parents are at their jobs. 396
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AR: Reviewer 2 should note that either choice [seasonal clocks and non-seasonal clocks] “allows the individual to 400

adjust their schedule out of personal preference.” Currently anyone can convince their co-workers to delay preset schedules in spring-summer. Anyone can also convince their co-workers to advance preset schedules in autumn-winter.

The thing to note is on which side the observer is. If the observer is contrarian, then they experiences hard times, regardless of whether permanent ST applies and they prefers a more advanced phase in spring-summer, or seasonal DST applies and they prefers a more delayed phase in spring-summer, or a more advanced phase in autumn-winter. Either choice would face the same issues: first convincing co-workers, then the many interactions with other societal issues that would not have followed their choice (“integration of various sectors of society”). This points to the synchronizing role of clock regulations. Those against the choice (seasonal clocks or no seasonal clocks) are out of sync with society.

RC: *27. the proposal around line 44 of page 8 parses what would happen with a 30 minute offset. this is currently the situation with communities on the edges of time zones.*

AR: Reviewer 2 ponders the time offset or the time position in a time zone and compares the current Western edge with the centre of the zone in the contra-factual (+0.5). They is partially right.

In this proposal we should also ponder the issue of seasons. Current setting is seasonal while the ST+0.5 is non-seasonal. In the end, it is not exactly the situation with communities on the edges of time zones.

Alternatively, we could say that the centre of the time zone would be in current the situation of the Western edge in autumn-winter, and in the current situation of the Eastern edge in spring-summer.

RC: *28. The last line of page 9 discusses early vs late risers. This somewhat confuses chronotype and work schedule, which do not necessarily align. There are late chronotypes and nonetheless need to rise early for their jobs.*

AR: Thank you very much for this comment. We have rewritten the Conclusion and this paragraph is no longer part of the submission.

Referring to the initial submission, we did not describe chronotypes. We just put forward work schedules as a descriptive variable. We understand that among the population of early risers there are people of either chronotype; the same happens for the late risers.

Indeed, this remark by reviewer 2 supports our point of view of seasonal DST as a compromise. If permanent DST is set, then, generally speaking, the early risers would be in a greater discomfort. Among them, those early risers with a later chronotype would be the group of population most in discomfort.

Likewise if permanent ST is set, then, generally speaking, the late risers would be in discomfort; those late riser with earliest chronotype would be the group of population most in discomfort.

4. Detailed response to Reviewer 3

Reviewer’s comments DOI: 10.1098/RSOS.240727/V1/REVIEW3 Reviewer 3 is anonymous.

We thank reviewer 3 for their comments.

RC: *I think that this is a potentially interesting paper but is really poorly written, does not have an argument, and comes to a conclusion that is not really “that DST” is rational, but it is unclear how the conclusion is*

formed, and what the author means by “rational”. I think the paper must have been written in Spanish and translated with google translate, it provides a set of disconnected sentences. See some examples, e.g., “cancel the regulations”, “we will not touch the energy savings” and there are a long list of sentences that need to be edited as they do not make sense as they are: “Worse, the preference for permanent DST still dominate polls.(Rubin, 2023)”.

AR: We never write a manuscript in Spanish language and then translate it into English. That would be really painful. Let alone, we do not make use of automated translators for that purpose. For their interest, we write the original manuscript in English. We sometimes test an automated translation from English into Spanish.

Our motivation is to describe the physiological and sociological roots of the clock regulations beyond the naive energy savings. We mainly address critical omissions in the current prevailing point.

We have rewritten the Conclusions, hopefully for the best.

5. Detailed response to Reviewer 4

Reviewer’s comments DOI: 10.1098/RSOS.240727/V1/REVIEW4 Reviewer 4 is Andrew N. Coogan.

We thank very much reviewer 4 for their comments. Short as they are, they address a critical aspect of our initial submission.

RC: *My main observation on the manuscript is what is meant by “misalignment”, as mentioned numerous times. I think the authors mean misalignment between human activity and the presence/absence of sunlight. I would argue from a chronobiological perspective that “misalignment” would be taken as referring to the mismatch between the timing activity versus the underpinning circadian phase of entrainment (for example as in Social Jetlag). This is an important distinction from a public health perspective as this conception of “misalignment” would be understood mechanistically to be risk factors for various physical and mental health conditions. Circadian phase of entrainment is of course linked to solar time, but imperfectly so in most modern contexts (eg. Zerbini et al, 2021; Skeldon and Dijk, 2017). Therefore human activity (which may be largely socially determined) may shift according to clock changes (as both the clock change and the social clock in general and working time practices are social constructions) but this shift in activity is not accompanied by a similar shift in circadian entrainment. Therefore DST may seem adaptive from an activity-social clock time perspective but may be maladaptive from an activity-circadian phase perspective. I would think this is an important that such considerations are discussed. It is also important impacts of clock changes on circadian clocks versus on sleep processes - these are linked, but not synonymous processes which can exert independent effects of behaviour, cognition and health. Therefore sleep duration should not be used as a proxy measure for circadian processes.*

AR: We found this comment really wonderful and indeed it has inspired much of our effort to bring the revised version. We agree with the distinction between activity-social and activity-circadian. We cannot provide an answer to whether seasonal DST is circadianly maladaptive because we do not have that expertise. Yet, we emphasize that evidence shows very clearly that seasonal DST has not been maladaptive from a social point of view. We address why. Interestingly the roots of DST regulations and their success can also be linked to human physiology.

In the initial submission we did not address the issue of SJL. In this new submission we address some issues connected to SJL. That being said, SJL was coined after clock regulations were enforced in many of

the countries where SJL studies have been conducted. So, yet again, deconfounding the impact of clock regulations from the impact of seasonal variations is even more problematic. In the revised submission we describe in some detail the well-known natural experiment analysed by Borisenkov et al. [23].

We agree that sleep duration should not be used as a proxy measure for circadian process. In our initial submission our aim was to highlight seasonal variations in sleep duration only to put forward that may not be related to DST but to seasons.

In the revised version we have added some reports of seasonal variability in sleep duration, again only to show that DST cannot be blamed for sleep loss during the summer season.

RC: *Overall, in the manuscript I found some of the arguments somewhat hard to follow. I think an edit of the manuscript could sharpen the arguments. In places the phraseology used make it harder to understand the intended argument. I think the manuscript could probably be shortened, and the introduction could be used to introduce the policy points to be later expanded on (how hazardous are the transitions etc). The policy recommendation s being made could be more explicitly expressed.*

AR: Thank you very much for this comment.

We have failed to make the revised submission shorter than the initial submission but, hopefully, the submission is now sharpened.

RC: *Some minor points: First line of the introduction, I don't think the clock change debate is on[e] the "most significant" science-policy issues (eg. compared to climate change). Maybe it is one of the more "visible" topics.*

AR: This is really a very good piece of advice. "Visible" is a most useful adjective here.

RC: *Page 2 line 55 - I would not refer to results from the 2018 EU survey due to the very low response rates of that survey and therefore the high risk of non-responder bias and un-representativeness in those results.*

AR: Thank you very much, again it is a very good remark. Indeed, we must acknowledge that we are having a hard time making this remark clear.

First, the public consultation did not have a very low response rate. The median value per Member State was some 0.36 % of population. This is peanuts in politics if we compare with the turnout of an election. It is peanuts if we wanted to assess the net balance of preferences by Member State. Nonetheless it is much greater than surveys and some other population studies, and it may be large enough if the goal is to understand the distribution of preferences (pro or against) across Geography.

To give an example Kantermann et al. [11] and the 2018 EU public consultation were both web-based, self-reported studies with little sample design. Kantermann et al. [11] is an aggregate study with most of the 55 000 respondents coming from Central Europe, mainly Germany, or some 0.09 % of population. The 2018 EU public consultation reports disaggregated values in 28 Member States from 35° to 60° latitude; the median value of the distribution of turnouts is 0.36 % of population.

Finally, whether or not the public consultation was able to retain unbiased properties of the underlying population, even though the shares of respondents were 0.36 % and there was no sample design, can only be addressed by a posterior analysis of the distribution of shares. It cannot be assessed from the aprioristic fact that uncontrolled factors existed, and that sample extraction was not designed.

The public consultation was a natural experiment. None was required to answer whether they likes or dislikes clock regulations. Instead, all were invited to have their say. Results show correlations between

the shares of population against DST and the latitude ($p = 0.08$; $N = 28$), the winter sunrise time ($p = 0.03$; $N = 28$), and, more importantly, the distance from the winter sunrise time to the start of human activity ($p = 5 \times 10^{-5}$; $N = 17$). Uncontrolled biases cannot build up correlations. Instead, the correlations suggest an interplay between the outcome (preferences against DST) and the descriptors (distance of work onset to SRW), that we link to human physiology.

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